

Information Rates of Sampled Wiener Processes

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Abstract—The minimal distortion attainable in recovering the waveform of a continuous-time Wiener process from an encoded version of its uniform samples is considered. We first introduce a combined sampling and source coding problem and prove an associated source coding theorem. We then derive an upper bound on the minimal distortion attainable under any sampling rate and a prescribed number of bits to encode the samples. We show that this bound is accurate to within a second order term in the sampling rate, and converges to the true distortion-rate function of the Wiener process as the sampling rate goes to infinity. For example, this bound implies that by providing a single bit per sample it is possible to achieve the optimal distortion-rate performance of the Wiener process, given by its distortion-rate function, to within a factor of 1.5. We conclude the distortion-rate function of the Wiener process is strictly smaller than the indirect distortion-rate function from its uniform samples obtained at any finite sampling rate. This is in contrast to stationary infinite bandwidth processes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consider the task of encoding a continuous-time random process with a constraint on the bitrate in this encoding. The optimal tradeoff between bitrate and distortion in the recovery of the process from its encoded version is described by its distortion-rate function (DRF). When the random process is bandlimited, each of its realizations assumes a discrete-time representation obtained by uniformly sampling above its Nyquist rate. This implies that a source coding theorem for bandlimited processes which provides a characterization of their DRF can be obtained directly from their discrete-time representations [1], [2].

In contrast to a bandlimited signal model, the Wiener process describes a continuous time phenomena whose time fluctuations scale with the time resolution, a property known as *scale-invariance* or *self-similarity*. In particular, it is impossible to obtain an equivalent discrete-time representation of this process by sampling its waveform at a finite sampling rate [3].

In theory it is possible to map each realization of a continuous-time Wiener process over a finite interval to a discrete sequence using the Karhunen-Löve (KL) transform. This transformation, together with an argument relating the encoding of the end-points of each finite interval, has led to a source coding theorem for the Wiener process [4]. In practice, however, the computation of the KL transform involves integration of the sample path of the process with respect to the KL basis elements. This integration, performed in continuous-time, is subject to severe inaccuracies as a result of the sample path fluctuation of the Wiener process. This limitation suggests that a more realistic way to describe performance limits in digitally encoding the Wiener process is by the combined sampling and source coding model described

Fig. 1: Uniform sampling and source coding system model.

in Fig. 1. In this model, the continuous-time Wiener process $W(\cdot)$ is first uniformly sampled at rate f_s , resulting in the discrete-time process $\bar{W}[\cdot]$. The process $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ is then encoded using no more than R bits per time unit, and ultimately the original waveform $W(\cdot)$ is reconstructed as accurately as possible from this encoded version. The parameters in this problem are the sampling rate f_s , the *bitrate* R and the average distortion D . The optimal tradeoff among the three is described by the function $D(f_s, R)$.

In this work we study the function $D(f_s, R)$ both at finite sampling rates f_s and asymptotically as $f_s \rightarrow \infty$. For the latter, we show that $D(f_s, R)$ converges to the DRF of $W(\cdot)$ from [4] and compute the rate of this convergence. In addition, we provide an upper bound on $D(f_s, R)$ which allows us to determine the sampling rate and the bitrate required in order to guarantee a prescribed target distortion in encoding a single realization of the Wiener process.

A. Related Works

The DRF of the Wiener process has been computed by Berger in [4]. Berger has also shown that this DRF is achievable even though the Wiener process is not stable. Gray established similar results for the more general family of unstable auto-regressive processes [5], but he did not consider the continuous-time case. The ideas behind Berger's and Gray's works were generalized to other non-stable signal models in [6]. Some issues involving the interaction between sampling and source coding were addressed in [1]. However, it seems that [2] provides the first full proof of a source coding theorem which is based on sampled data, but only for stationary processes as the sampling rate goes to infinity. The non-asymptotic case of the sampling rate was considered in [7] using a combined sampling and source coding model similar to Fig. 1. The main result of [7] is a full characterization of the counterpart of $D(f_s, R)$ for stationary Gaussian processes in terms of their spectrum. When pre-processing before sampling is allowed, it was shown that even when the source is not bandlimited, its distortion-rate function can be attained by

sampling above a critical *finite* rate which depends on the bitrate [8]. The current work can be seen as an extension of [7] to a particular non-stationary source, namely the Wiener process.

B. Contributions

The main contribution of this paper is an upper bound on the function $D(f_s, R)$. This upper bound is shown to be tight to a first order in f_s as f_s goes to infinity. This result allows the determination of the sampling rate and bit rate required in order to guarantee a prescribed target bit distortion. For example, we show that by sampling at a rate of R , thus providing a single bit per sample, it is possible to achieve distortion which is about 1.5 times larger than the DRF of the Wiener process for the same bitrate R . In addition, our characterization proves that the DRF of the Wiener process is strictly smaller than the performance achieved by encoding the samples for any finite sampling rate. This last fact is in contrast to the case of other Gaussian signal models. In particular, we show in [8] that for certain types of Gaussian infinite-bandwidth signal models, the DRF is achieved above a finite sampling rate.

In addition to this upper bound, we prove a source coding theorem for a combined sampling and source coding problem with a continuous-time Wiener process as a source. We show that the minimal distortion in this problem converges to the DRF of the Wiener process as the sampling rate goes to infinity. This last fact provides an alternative way of computing the DRF of the Wiener process, and shows that the latter is attainable by uniformly sampling at a rate arbitrarily high. This last fact also settles an interesting observation made in [4] about the equivalence of the DRF of a discrete-time Wiener process at high distortion to the DRF of the continuous-time Wiener process.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in Section II we define a combined sampling and source coding problem for the Wiener process. Preliminary results are provided in Section III. Our main results are given in Section IV. Concluding remarks can be found in Section V.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Our signal model is a continuous-time Gaussian process $W(\cdot) = \{W(t), t > 0\}$ with zero mean and covariance function

$$K_W(t, s) \triangleq \mathbb{E}[W(t)W(s)] = \sigma^2 \min\{t, s\}, \quad t, s \geq 0.$$

We consider the system depicted in Fig. 1 to describe the random waveform $W(0 : T) \triangleq \{W(t), t \in [0, T]\}$ using a sequence of codes of rate R bits per time unit. Unlike in the regular source coding problem for the Wiener process considered in [4], our setting assumes that $W(0 : T)$ is first uniformly sampled at frequency f_s . This sampling leads to the finite random vector

$$\bar{W}[0 : T f_s] \triangleq \{W(n/f_s), n \in \mathbb{N} \cap [0, f_s T]\}. \quad (1)$$

Next, the vector $\bar{W}[0 : T f_s]$ is mapped by the *encoder* to an index $Z_T \in \{1, \dots, 2^{RT}\}$. The *decoder*, upon receiving Z_T , provides an estimate $\hat{W}(0 : T) = \{\hat{W}(t), t \in [0, T]\}$ which is only a function of Z_T .

The optimal performance theoretical achievable (OPTA) distortion in estimating $W(\cdot)$ from its samples $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ is defined as

$$D^{OPTA}(R) = \inf_T D_T^{OPTA}(R)$$

where

$$D_T^{OPTA}(R) = \inf \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \mathbb{E} \left(W(t) - \hat{W}(t) \right)^2 dt,$$

and the infimum is taken over all encoder-decoder mappings

$$\bar{W}[0 : T f_s] \rightarrow Z_T \rightarrow \hat{W}(0 : T).$$

The characterization of $D_T^{OPTA}(R)$ in terms of an optimization problem involving mutual information between probability distributions is one of the results in this paper, given in the next section.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We begin by proving a source coding theorem for the combined sampling and source coding problem presented in Section II.

A. Source Coding Theorem

Theorem 1: Let

$$D_{W|\bar{W}}(R) = \liminf_{T \rightarrow \infty} D_T(R), \quad (2)$$

where

$$D_T(R) = \inf \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \mathbb{E} \left(W(t) - \hat{W}(t) \right)^2 dt,$$

and the infimum is taken over all joint distributions $p(\bar{W}[0 : T f_s], \hat{W}(0 : T))$ such that the mutual information rate

$$f_s I(\bar{W}[0 : T f_s]; \hat{W}(0 : T)) \quad (3)$$

is limited to R bits per time unit. Then

$$D^{OPTA}(R) = D_{W|\bar{W}}(R).$$

The proof of this theorem is obtained by using the change of measure idea in remote source coding from [1] and by separately encoding the endpoints of intervals of length T as in [4]. The details can be found in [9].

Note that $D_{W|\bar{W}}(R)$ implicitly depends on the sampling rate f_s through the definition of the process $\hat{W}[\cdot]$ in (1). In order to make this dependency explicit, we henceforth use the notation

$$D_W(f_s, R) \triangleq D_{W|\bar{W}}(R).$$

From the definition of $D_W(f_s, R)$ in Section II it immediately follows that

$$D_W(f_s, R) \geq \max \{ \text{mmse}(W|\bar{W}), D_W(R) \},$$

where $\text{mmse}(W|\bar{W})$ is the minimal mean squared error (MMSE) in estimating a sample path of the Wiener process given its uniform samples at rate f_s , and $D_W(R)$ is the DRF of the Wiener process. Below we discuss previous results in source coding theory with respect to these two quantities, and prove some new results which will be used in Section IV.

B. Information Rates of Wiener Processes

The DRF of the Wiener process $W(\cdot)$ is given by [4]

$$D_W(R) = \frac{2\sigma^2}{\pi^2 \ln 2} R^{-1} \approx 0.292\sigma^2 R^{-1} \left[\frac{\text{MSE} \times \text{sec}}{\text{bits}} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Note that since

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{W}[n]\bar{W}[k]) = \mathbb{E}(\bar{W}(n/f_s)W(k/f_s)) = \sigma^2 \min\{n, k\}/f_s,$$

the process $\bar{W}[\cdot] = \{W(n/f_s), n = 0, 1, \dots\}$ defines a discrete-time Wiener process with intensity σ^2/f_s . Using Berger's expression from [4] for the DRF of a discrete-time Wiener process, we conclude that $D_{\bar{W}}(\bar{R})$, the DRF of $\bar{W}[\cdot]$, is given by the following parametric form

$$\begin{aligned} D(\theta) &= \frac{\sigma^2}{f_s} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{4 \sin^2(\pi\phi/2)}, \theta \right\} d\phi, \\ \bar{R}(\theta) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \log^+ \left[\frac{1}{4\theta \sin^2(\pi\phi/2)} \right] d\phi, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where here \bar{R} is measured in bits per sample¹. Keeping the bitrate $R = f_s \bar{R}$ fixed and increasing f_s , we see that the asymptotic behavior of the DRF of $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ as f_s goes infinity is given by (5) when \bar{R} goes to zero or, equivalently, when θ goes to infinity. The latter can be obtained by expanding both expressions in (5) according to θ^{-1} , which, after eliminating θ leads to

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\bar{W}}(\bar{R}) &\sim \frac{\sigma^2}{f_s} \left(\frac{2}{\pi^2 \ln 2 \bar{R}} + \frac{\bar{R} \ln 2}{12} + O(\bar{R}^{-2}) \right) \\ &= \frac{2\sigma^2}{\pi^2 \ln 2} R^{-1} + \frac{\ln 2 \sigma^2}{12} \frac{R}{f_s^2} + O(f_s^{-3}). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The first term in (6) is the DRF of the continuous-time Wiener process (4). Thus, we have proved the following proposition:

Proposition 2: Let $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ be the process obtained by uniformly sampling the Wiener process $W(\cdot)$ at frequency f_s . We have

$$\lim_{f_s \rightarrow \infty} D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s) = D_W(R).$$

In fact, it can easily be shown that $D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s)$ is monotonically increasing in f_s so that

$$\sup_{f_s > 0} D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s) = D_W(R). \quad (7)$$

Proposition (2) provides an intuitive explanation to an interesting fact observed in [4], which says that the DRF of a discrete time Wiener process in high distortion behaves as the DRF of a continuous-time Wiener process. Proposition 2

¹This is consistent with our previous notations since $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ is a discrete-time process and the code rate is measured in bits per source symbol.

Fig. 2: Sample paths of $W(\cdot)$ (blue), $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ (black) and $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ (red).

shows that this fact is simply the result of evaluating the DRF of the discrete-time Wiener process $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ at high sampling rate, while holding the bitrate R constant. As a result of the high sampling rate, the number of bits per sample $\bar{R} = R/f_s$ goes to zero and the DRF of the discrete-time Wiener process is evaluated at the large distortion (low bit) limit.

C. MMSE Estimation from Sampled Data

On the other extreme of the combined sampling and source coding problem of Fig. 1 is the relaxation of the bitrate constraint by letting $R \rightarrow \infty$. Under this relaxation, the function $D_W(f_s, R)$ reduces to the MMSE in estimating $W(\cdot)$ from its uniform samples $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ at sampling frequency T_s^{-1} , denoted $\text{mmse}(W|\bar{W})$. For $t > 0$, denote by t^+ and t^- the two points on the grid $\mathbb{Z}T_s$ closest to t , namely, $t^- = \lfloor t/T_s \rfloor T_s$ and $t^+ = \lceil t/T_s \rceil T_s$. Due to the Markov property of $W(\cdot)$, the MMSE estimation of $W(t)$ from $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ is given by a linear interpolation between these two points:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{W}(t) &\triangleq \mathbb{E}[W(t)|\bar{W}[\cdot]] = \mathbb{E}[W(t)|W(t^+), W(t^-)] \\ &= \frac{t^+ - t}{T_s} W(t^-) + \frac{t - t^-}{T_s} W(t^+). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

A typical realization of the processes $W(\cdot)$, $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ and $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ is illustrated in Fig. 2.

The estimation error $B(t) \triangleq W(t) - \tilde{W}(t)$ defines a *Brownian bridge* on any interval whose endpoints are on the grid $\mathbb{Z}T_s$. The correlation function of $B(\cdot)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} K_B(t, s) &= \mathbb{E}[B(t)B(s)] \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{T_s} \begin{cases} (t^+ - t \vee s)(t \wedge s - t^-) & nT_s \leq t, s \leq (n+1)T_s, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $t \vee s$ and $t \wedge s$ denote the maximum and minimum of $\{t, s\}$, respectively. In particular, we conclude that

$$\text{mmse}(W(t)|\bar{W}) = K_B(t, t) = \frac{\sigma^2}{T_s} (t^+ - t)(t - t^-),$$

and

$$\text{mmse}(W|\bar{W}) = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_{nT_s}^{(n+1)T_s} K_B(t, t) dt = \frac{\sigma^2 T_s}{6} = \frac{\sigma^2}{6f_s}. \quad (10)$$

D. Indirect Distortion-Rate

Note that in the setting of Fig. 1 it is required to provide an estimate of $W(\cdot)$ but without directly observing its realizations. Therefore, our sampling and source coding problem can be seen as an *indirect* or *remote* source coding problem [1],

Fig. 3: Relations among the processes $W(\cdot)$, $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$, $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ and their associated distortion functions. Each reconstruction operation is associated with a distortion quantity. In this paper we show that $D_{\tilde{W}}(R) \leq D_{\tilde{W}}(R/f_s) \leq D_W(R) \leq D_W(f_s, R) \leq \bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$, where the latter equals $\text{mmse}(W|\tilde{W}) + D_{\tilde{W}}(R/f_s)$.

and the function $D_W(f_s, R)$ is denoted the *indirect* distortion-rate function (iDRF) of $W(\cdot)$ given $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$. A well known decomposition of this iDRF (e.g. [10] and [11]) leads to

$$D(f_s, R) = \text{mmse}(W|\tilde{W}) + D_{\tilde{W}}(R), \quad (11)$$

where $D_{\tilde{W}}(R)$ is the (direct) DRF of the process $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ of (8) which is the MMSE estimator of $W(t)$ from $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$. The representation (11) implies that $D(f_s, R)$ can be found by evaluating the function $D_{\tilde{W}}(R)$. However, the lack of stationarity or other structure on the process $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ makes such an evaluation a challenging task. Our main result, presented in the following section, will lead to an upper bound on $D_{\tilde{W}}(R)$ that will be enough to determine the rate at which $D_W(f_s, R)$ converges to $D_W(R)$ as $f_s \rightarrow \infty$.

The various quantities defined so far and the relationship among them are illustrated in the diagram in Fig. 3.

IV. MAIN RESULTS

Our main result with respect to the function $D_W(f_s, R)$ is given in the following subsection. Its significance is subsequently discussed.

A. Discrete-Time Interpolation Upper Bound

In this subsection we derive an upper bound on the function $D_W(f_s, R)$ which is inspired by the following achievable scheme for encoding the process $\tilde{W}(R)$ of (8): encode the samples using a rate- R code that approaches the DRF of the process $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$, and consequently recover the continuous-time process $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ by a linear interpolation similar to (8). We have the following results:

Proposition 3: The distortion-rate function of the estimator $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ of the Wiener process $W(\cdot)$ from its uniform samples at rate f_s satisfies

$$D_{\tilde{W}}(R) \leq D_{\tilde{W}}(R/f_s), \quad (12)$$

where $D_{\tilde{W}}(\bar{R})$ is the DRF of the discrete-time process obtained by uniformly sampling $W(\cdot)$ at rate f_s evaluated at rate \bar{R} bits per source sample.

Proof sketch: The bound (12) is obtained by taking the reconstruction of $\tilde{W}(\cdot)$ in the interval $[nT_s, (n+1)T_s]$ to an interpolation of the form (8) between $\hat{W}[n]$ and $\hat{W}[n+1]$, where $\hat{W}[\cdot]$ is a reconstruction of $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$ that approaches its distortion-rate function at rate $\bar{R} = R/f_s$. The details can be

Fig. 4: The functions $D_W(R)$, $D_{\tilde{W}}(R/f_s)$, $\text{mmse}(W|\tilde{W})$ and the upper bound $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$. The dotted line describes a possible behavior of $D(f_s, R)$. Up: $R = 1$ bit per second and varying f_s . Bottom: $f_s = 1$ sample per second and varying R .

found in [9].

Define the following function:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{D}(f_s, R) &\triangleq \text{mmse}(W|\tilde{W}) + D_{\tilde{W}}(R/f_s) \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{6f_s} + \frac{\sigma^2}{f_s} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{4\sin^2(\pi\phi/2)}, \theta \right\} d\phi, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where θ is determined by

$$R(\theta) = \frac{f_s}{2} \int_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \log^+ \left[\frac{1}{4\theta \sin^2(\pi\phi/2)} \right] df.$$

We now obtain the following theorem:

Theorem 4: For any $R > 0$ and $f_s >$, the indirect distortion-rate function of the Wiener process $W(\cdot)$ from its samples $\tilde{W}[\cdot]$ satisfies

$$D(f_s, R) \leq \bar{D}(f_s, R),$$

where $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$ is given by (13).

Proof: The theorem follows from Proposition 3 and (5) and (10) applied to (11). \square

The bound $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ is illustrated along with $\text{mmse}(W|\bar{W})$, $D_W(R)$, and $D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s)$ in Fig. 4.

B. Discussion

It is convenient to analyze the bound $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ in low and high sampling rates separately.

Low sampling rates: When $f_s \leq R$ the bound (13) reduces to

$$D_W(f_s, R) \leq \frac{\sigma^2}{f_s} \left(\frac{1}{6} + 2^{-2R/f_s} \right). \quad (14)$$

If we choose the sampling rate as $f_s = R$ samples per seconds we obtain

$$D_W(f_s, R) \leq \frac{5}{12} \sigma^2 R^{-1} = 0.4167 \sigma^2 R^{-1}, \quad (15)$$

which is larger than the true DRF of $W(\cdot)$ by a factor of approximately 1.427. Other choices of $f_s < R$ lead to a higher value in (14). Equation (15) implies that when $f_s \leq R$, there is not much gain in increasing the number of bits per sample above $\log(6) \approx 1.3$.

High sampling rates: It follows from (6) that in the limit of a large sampling rate,

$$\bar{D}_W(f_s, R) = \frac{\sigma^2}{6f_s} + \frac{2\sigma^2}{\pi^2 \ln 2} R^{-1} + O(f_s^{-2}). \quad (16)$$

Moreover, since $D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s)$ converges monotonically to $D_W(R)$, the first two terms in the RHS of (16) provides an upper bound on $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ which holds for any $f_s > 0$. This bound implies that for all $\alpha > 0$,

$$\frac{\bar{D}_W(\alpha R, R)}{D_W(R)} \leq 1 + \frac{\pi^2 \ln 2}{12\alpha} \approx 1 + 0.57\alpha^{-1}.$$

That is, a sampling rate of $f_s = \alpha R$ is enough to achieve the optimal performance to within a factor of $1 + 0.57\alpha^{-1}$.

The main reason why the bound $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$ is not tight can be described as *mismatched encoding*. That is, $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$ is obtained by encoding $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ in a way which is optimal to minimize the quadratic distortion between $\bar{W}[\cdot]$ and its reconstruction process $\hat{W}[\cdot]$ as illustrated in Fig. 3. However, remote source coding theory tells us that an optimal coding scheme for $\bar{W}(\cdot)$ is obtained by first estimating (non-causally) $\bar{W}(\cdot)$ from $\bar{W}[\cdot]$, and then applying an optimal code with respect to this estimator. The bound $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$ is obtained by reversing the order of encoding and estimation, what leads to sub-optimal performance in general [12]. Since the sample paths of the two processes converge to each other as f_s increases, this mismatch in encoding does not play a significant role at high sampling rates.

C. Convergence Rate

Although not tight, the bound $\bar{D}(f_s, R)$ is enough to determine the convergence rate of $D_W(f_s, R)$ to $D_W(R)$ in Proposition 2:

Corollary 5: For all $R > 0$, we have

$$D_W(f_s, R) - D_W(R) = \frac{\sigma^2}{6f_s} + O(f_s^{-2}).$$

Proof: The fact that $D_W(f_s, R)$ converges to $D_W(R)$ no faster than $1/f_s$ follows from (11). From (6) it follows that the $1/f_s$ term of $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ is $\sigma^2/(6f_s)$, as there are no $1/f_s$ terms in $D_{\bar{W}}(R/f_s)$. \square

Note that the $1/f_s$ term in (13) implies that the number of bits per sample R/f_s must go to zero in order for $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ to converge to $D_W(R)$, as can be seen in Fig. 4. It is not yet clear whether $D_W(f_s, R)$ and $\bar{D}_W(f_s, R)$ share the same $1/f_s^2$ term, given by (6).

As a result of Corollary 5 we conclude that $D_W(f_s, R)$ is strictly larger than $D_W(R)$ for any finite sampling rate f_s . This last property is in contrast to the iDRF from samples of stationary processes with a non-flat spectrum, such as the Gauss-Markov process. Even if such a process is not bandlimited, it is shown in [8] that there still exists a critical sampling frequency above which there is no loss in performance compared to the infinite sampling rate distortion.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We derived an upper bound on the minimal distortion attainable in estimating the path of a continuous-time Wiener process from a bitrate-limited version of its uniform samples, taken at a finite sampling rate. By doing so we characterized the rate at which this distortion converges to the standard distortion-rate function of the Wiener process as the sampling rate increases. This characterization allows us to determine the sampling rate and the number of bits per time unit required to achieve a prescribed target distortion. For example, we conclude that one bit per sample is enough to achieve 1.5 times the optimal distortion-rate performance.

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